

Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya as Determinants of Cellular Health: A Unani Framework for Lifestyle Disorders

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Abstract

Unani medicine gives primary importance to prevention of disease rather than mere treatment of disease. *Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya* refers to the six essential factors that bring continuous changes (Taghayyur) in the body (badan) and help maintain protection to the body. These factors are those from which a person cannot get rid from the rest of his life. These factors play a vital role in maintaining normal *Mizāj*, proper formation of *Akhlāt*, and efficient functioning of bodily faculties. Ancient unani studies show that the determinants of lifestyle disorders include imbalance in sleep, dietary habits. In Modern perspective, concepts such as cellular metabolism, hormonal imbalance show similarity with the mechanisms of these disorders. The present paper highlights how disturbance of these six essential factors leads to impaired cellular nutrition and gradual development of lifestyle disorders. In the Unani system of medicine the main emphasis of the principle of treatment (*Usool-e-Ilaj*) is to correct the abnormal constitution (*Su-e-Mizaj*) and alter the six prerequisites for existence (*Asbab-e-Sitta Zarooriya*) to restore normal health. Understanding *Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya* in the light of cellular health provides a strong preventive framework that is highly relevant in present-day healthcare.

KEYWORD: *Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya, Mizāj, Taghayyur, cellular health, preventive medicine.*

1. Introduction

The Unani system is a holistic approach that focuses more on prevention than the treatment. The concept of Hifz -e- sehat (preservation of health) forms the fundamental basis of the unani system . The core principle of Unani is balancing of humours, Quwwat mudabera-e-badan , balanced diet, adequate sleep, physical activity and proper environmental exposure play an important role in maintaining normal health of the body. Before the development of modern preventive medicine practices, Unani scholars emphasized that disease before its progression and corrective measures should be taken timely.

The Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarūriyya are one of the core principles of Unani medicine. This includes air (Hawā), food and drink (Makool wa Mashroob), physical movement and rest (Harkat wa Sukoon-e-Badani), mental movement and rest (Harkat wa Sukoon-e-Nafsani), sleep and wakefulness (Naum wa Yaqzah), retention and excretion (Ehtebas wa Istifragh). These factors affect the body in such a way that due to their disturbance may lead to disorders like disturbed sleep, malnutrition, obesity, lethargy. In the Unani system, proper maintenance of these factors influences the Mizaj of the body, balanced Akhlāt, ensure efficient functioning of bodily faculties and bring about physiological changes known as Taghayyur-e-Sehat.

In the modern period, rapid changes in lifestyle have resulted in disturbance of the Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya. Irregular sleep patterns, unhealthy dietary habits and mental stress have become common contributing factors. Ancient Unani literature emphasizes that such imbalance in these essential factors leads to loss of moderation (I'tidāl), which is gradually becoming a cause of various chronic and lifestyle disorders.

Modern medicine explains the development of lifestyle disorders at the cellular level, which include alterations in cellular metabolism, hormonal regulation and nutrient utilization. Disturbance at cellular nutrition, metabolic dysfunction now underline many chronic and lifestyle disorders. When viewed in literature, Modern explanations of disease causation align with the Unani concept Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya. However, limited efforts have been made to interpret these classical principles scientifically. Therefore, the present study aims to understand Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya from a cellular perspective and to highlight the significance in preventive medicine within present-day healthcare.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Concept of Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya in Unani Medicine

Unani scholars such as Ibn Sina , Jalenus and Razius described Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya as essential external factors necessary for survival and health. Proper quality of air maintains Hararat-e-Ghariziya of a body. Balanced diet provide nourishment for formation of healthy Akhlāṭ.of the body. Physical and mental activities must be moderate to preserve strength of faculties.Adequate sleep restores energy, while proper retention and evacuation help in removal of waste products.

2.2 Role of Asbāb-e-Sitta in Maintenance of Mizāj and Cellular Nutrition

Balanced Asbāb-e-Sitta maintain equilibrium of Mizaj and support proper cellular nutrition. Nutrition reaches tissues through well formed Akhlāṭ, any disturbance in this process affect this process. Proper functioning of Quwwat-e-Mudabbira-e-Badan ensures utilization of nutrients at tissues and cellular level.

2.3 Derangement of Asbāb-e-Sitta and Development of Lifestyle Disorders

Unbalanced diet, disturbed sleep, sedentary lifestyle and chronic mental stress lead to derangement of these factors.Over times, this result in weakness of bodily faculties and improper tissue nourishment. Such gradual changes from the basics of lifestyle disorder, which initially remain subclinical and later manifest as chronic disease.

3. CORRELATION WITH MODERN CONCEPT OF CELLULAR HEALTH

Modern science recognizes that lifestyle factors directly influence cellular metabolism and function. Poor diet affects energy production, while lack of physical activity reduces mitochondria efficiency. Disturbed sleep influences change in hormonal balance and alters cardiac rhythm, leading to metabolic dysfunction. Psychological stress increases inflammatory mediators that impair cellular repair. These changes can be correlated with unani concepts such as *Zof-e-Quwwat, Ikhtilal-e-Hararat, and Fasad-e-Mizāj.*

4. Material & Methods (Literary)

This study is a literary review based on classical Unani texts including Al-Qanoon fi al-Tibb, Kitab al-Hawi, Zakhira Khwarazm Shahi and Kulliyat-e-Nafisi. Modern references were collected from PubMed, Google Scholar and WHO publications related to lifestyle disorders and cellular metabolism. Keywords used included “cellular metabolism”, “lifestyle disorder”, “preventive medicine”, “Unani”, and “Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya”. Relevant literature was analysed to identify correlations between classical concepts and modern scientific understanding.

5. DISCUSSION

The Unani framework of Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya comprehensive preventive through addressing lifestyle disorders. Modern medicine now uses the same principle through cellular nutrition and metabolic research. Integrating these perspectives can strengthen preventive healthcare strategies and reduce the burden of lifestyle disorders.

6. Conclusion

Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya play an important role in preservation of health by maintaining cellular balance and tissue nutrition. Their proper regulation can prevent lifestyle disorders. Understanding these concepts within the present day highlights the relevance of Unani preventive medicine in contemporary healthcare.

7. Refrence

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